

Dinuclear complexes of bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg with bis-bidentate oxygen donor azodye ligands

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Fourteen dimeric metal complexes of composition $[M_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$ and $[M_2^1LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$, $[M_2L^1(H_2O)_8]$ and $[M_2^1L^1(H_2O)_4]$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$, $M^1 = Cd^{II}$ and Hg^{II} , $LH_2 = 4,4'$ -di(3'-aldehydo-4'-hydroxyphenylazo)diphenyl ether; $L^1H_4 = 4,4'$ -di(3'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenylazo)diphenyl ether, have been prepared.

In continuation of our work on the synthesis of a number of multidonor azodyes and their polymeric complexes, we report here the preparation and characterization of two new bis-bidentate azodyes and their dimeric complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} .

Results and Discussion

The dimeric metal complexes have the composition $[M_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$, $[M_2^1LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$, $[M_2L^1(H_2O)_8]$ and $[M_2^1L^1(H_2O)_4]$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$, $M^1 = Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}$; $LH_2 = 4,4'$ -di(3'-aldehydo-4'-hydroxyphenylazo)-diphenyl ether; $L^1H_4 = 4,4'$ -di(3'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenylazo)diphenyl ether. All the complexes are stable at room temperature (d.p. $>140^\circ$), having coordinated water molecules. They are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in dimethylformamide and non-electrolytic in nature ($\Lambda_M = 4.7-5.9 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$).

The ligands revealed a broad IR band at $3500 (LH_2)/3237 cm^{-1} (L^1H_4)$ (intramolecular O-H...O hydrogen bonding) and its absence in metal chelates indicates the deprotonation of phenolic protons, thereby suggesting the bonding of phenolic oxygen atoms to the metal atoms¹. The ligand bands at $1579 (LH_2)$ and $1583 cm^{-1} (L^1H_4)$ can be attributed to azo $-N=N-$ vibrations which remained unaltered in the complexes indicating the non-coordination of the azo nitrogen atoms. The $\nu_{C=O}$ ligand bands at $1240 (LH_2)$ and $1247 cm^{-1} (L^1H_4)$ underwent downward shift in the complexes showing the bonding of phenolic oxygen atoms to the metal atoms. In the ligand (LH_2), the sharp band observed around $1659 cm^{-1}$ can be assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ vibrations and in the metal complexes it appeared at $\sim 1620 cm^{-1}$, suggesting the bonding of the ligand to the metal ions through carbonyl oxygen atoms. In ligand L^1H_4 , the $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ and

$\nu_s(COO^-)$ bands appear around 1663 and $1444 cm^{-1}$, respectively, and these bands are observed in the complexes at ~ 1599 and $\sim 1400 cm^{-1}$ with a difference of ($\Delta\nu$) of $\sim 200 cm^{-1}$, supporting the monodentate nature of the carboxylate groups². In all the complexes, the bands around ~ 3553 , 3370 , 3184 and $833-840 cm^{-1}$, could be assigned to OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations, respectively, which show the presence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes³. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligands to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of a new band at $484-495 cm^{-1} (M-O)$ in the far-IR spectra of the complexes⁴. The μ_{eff} values of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were found to ~ 5.0 , 3.0 , 3.65 and 1.80 B.M., indicating octahedral configuration of the complexes⁵.

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic moment data of the complexes

Compd.	Colour	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
LH_2	Red	—	—
L^1H_4	Red	—	—
$[Mn_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Brown	14.2 (14.6)	3.65
$[Mn_2L^1(H_2O)_8]$	Brown	14.4 (14.7)	3.67
$[Co_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Red	15.1 (15.5)	5.0
$[Co_2L^1(H_2O)_8]$	Red	15.3 (15.6)	5.1
$[Ni_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Brown	15.2 (15.4)	3.0
$[Ni_2L^1(H_2O)_8]$	Brown	15.3 (15.5)	2.9
$[Cu_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Brown	16.3 (16.5)	1.80
$[Cu_2L^1(H_2O)_8]$	Brown	16.4 (16.6)	1.79
$[Zn_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Red	16.5 (16.9)	—
$[Zn_2L^1(H_2O)_8]$	Red	16.7 (17.0)	—
$[Cd_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	Brown	28.1 (28.2)	—
$[Cd_2L^1(H_2O)_4]$	Pink	28.1 (28.4)	—
$[Hg_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	White	41.0 (41.3)	—
$[Hg_2L^1(H_2O)_4]$	White	41.1 (41.5)	—

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes revealed bands at 8875 (8885), 17830 (17895), 20700 (20730) and 32310 (32350) cm^{-1} . The first three bands can be assigned

to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(v_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(v_2)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ transitions and the last band to a CT band. The calculated ligand field parameters like $D_q = 895.5$ (901.0) cm^{-1} , $B = 793.6$ (798.0) cm^{-1} , $\beta_{35} = 0.815$ (0.820), $v_2/v_1 = 2.01$ (2.01) and $\sigma = 22.7$ (21.95) suggest an octahedral geometry for the complexes⁶. In the electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes, one broad asymmetric band appeared at $\sim 13415\text{--}14720$ cm^{-1} with a maxima at 14330 (14310) cm^{-1} which could be attributed to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transitions proposing a distorted octahedral stereochemistry around the metal ions⁷. The Ni^{II} complexes showed bands at 10120 (10105), 16880 (16910), 24770 (24830) and 32470 (32490) cm^{-1} , assignable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(v_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(n_2)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ and CT transitions, respectively, in a distorted octahedral symmetry field⁸. The ligand field parameters like $D_q = 1012$ (1010) cm^{-1} , $B = 752.6$ (761.6) cm^{-1} , $\beta_{35} = 0.723$ (0.731), $v_2/v_1 = 1.66$ (1.67) and $\sigma = 38.31$ (36.79) also confirm an octahedral stereochemistry for these complexes. The electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes exhibited bands at 18220 (18155), 24430 (24475) and 27170 (27250) cm^{-1} attributable to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$, respectively, supporting an octahedral geometry for the complexes⁹.

The ESR spectra of the polycrystalline Cu^{II} complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ and $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}^1(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]$ at X-band (RT) revealed the g_{av} values 2.05738 and 2.05740 , respectively. The g values (< 2.3) indicate the covalent nature of the M–L bond. These values are consistent with the Cu–O bonded copper complexes¹⁰.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of ligand (LH_2) displayed a complex pattern at δ 8.43–8.74 due to fourteen aromatic protons. The peaks at δ 11.55 and 9.69 correspond to phenolic and aldehydic protons, respectively. In ligand (L^1H_4), the complex pattern was observed at δ 6.9–8.4 due to fourteen aromatic protons. The phenolic and carboxylic protons of this ligand was not recorded.

The XRD study (powdered pattern) of the complex $[\text{Cd}_2\text{L}^1(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ was indexed and the unit cell parameters like a , b , c , α , β , γ and the volume of the unit cell were found to be 12.192 Å, 27.824 , 9.911 , 92.981° , 104.703° , 94.998° and 3230.18 Å³, respectively, and these values are in agreement with the triclinic structure of the cadmium complex. The molecular weight of the compound calculated was 790.8 . The density of the compound was found to be 0.81 g/ml. The number of formula units was found to be 2 which is compatible to triclinic unit cell and it is inferred that there is a centre of symmetry in the complex and the structure of the complex corresponds to the triclinic system.

The Zn^{II} complex was found to be hexacoordinated with an octahedral geometry, and the Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes were found to be tetraordinated with a tetrahedral geometry based upon analytical and spectral data. Hence both the azodyes LH_2 and L^1H_4 behave as bisbidentate ligands, bonded to metal ions through phenolic oxygen, carbonyl oxygen and carboxyl oxygen atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. make. The ligand LH_2 and L^1H_4 were prepared by the coupling reaction¹¹ of the diazonium chloride obtained from 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl ether with salicylaldehyde and salicylic acid at 0° , respectively.

Preparation of the complexes: A mixture of ethanolic solution of metal chlorides and a solution of the azo dye in 1,4-dioxan (in 2 : 1 molar ratio) was refluxed for 0.5 h. On cooling, conc. ammonium hydroxide was added dropwise and the metal complexes formed were washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal and nitrogen contents were estimated by standard methods¹². Conductance was measured in 10^{-3} M DMF solutions. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Hilger and Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer, NMR spectra (acetone- d_6) on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer at RT, and ESR spectra at RT on a Varian E₄ spectrometer. X-Ray diffraction was recorded in a Phillips PW 1130 instrument.

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